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Impact of anteroposterior pelvic diameter on ^{99m}Tc-mercaptoacetyltryglycine diuretic renography

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Introduction: Antenatal hydronephrosis is the most commonly detected abnormality during fetal development. The aim of the study was to evaluate whether the size of the prenatal and postnatal renal pelvic anteroposterior diameter (APD) has prediction of obstruction drainage finding on diuretic renography and impaired renal function.

Methods: We prospectively studied 32 renal units with prenataly diagnosed hydronephrosis, that was confirmed on postnatal ultrasonography. The renal pelvic APD was measured in pregnancy between 17th and 35th week of gestation, and between 1st and 4th week after birth to confirm hydronephrosis. The initial ^{99m}Tc-MAG3 was performed in all patients between 4th and 8th week after birth. All patients were divided into two groups: the first group included patients with obstructive diuretic renography finding and the second one included patients with non-obstructive finding.

Results: Out of 32 renal units with hydronephrosis, 14 had obstructive pattern on diuretic renography, and 18 had non-obstructive hydronephrosis. The average of prenatal renal pelvic APD in the first group was statistically higher than in the second one ($p=0.009$). The average of postnatal renal pelvic APD in the obstructive group was also statistically higher than in the non-obstructive group ($p=0.0006$). The presence of impaired renal function (less than 40%) was significantly more frequent in the obstructive group.

Conclusion: Our study showed that the grade of both renal pelvic diameter, more prominent postnatal, have a significant impact on scintigraphy finding.

Key words: Hydronephrosis; Kidney Pelvis; Ultrasonography; Prenatal Diagnosis; Radioisotope Renography; Infant, Newborn; Technetium Tc 99m Mertiotide

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Correlation between Gleason score level, prostate specific antigen levels and bone scintigraphy in newly diagnosed prostatic cancer patients

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Introduction: The aim of this study was to identify correlation between Gleason score (GS), and prostate specific antigen levels (PSA), with bone metastasis in newly diagnosed prostate cancer patients.

Methods: This retrospective study included 298 patients with prostatic cancer in region of Vojvodina from 2012 to 2014., who had PSA, histological confirmation of prostatic cancer (GS) and bone scan. PSA was measured using hemiluminescent method, on Architect i2000SR automatic system, and histological examination was graded according to Gleason's grading system as: well differentiated (GS ≤6), moderately differentiated (GS =7), and poorly differentiated (GS ≥8). Bone scintigraphy was performed 2 to 4 hours after i.v application of radiotracer agent ^{99m}Tc- diphosphonate (DPD) in dose of 555 MBq. The patients were divided into 2 groups based on bone scintigraphy findings.

Results: The patients with negative bone scan (129/298) had the average level of PSA 14 ng/ml, the mean age was 69.8±/6.4 years and GS was 6.5±/1.24. The patients with positive bone scan (169/298) finding had the average PSA level 50 ng/ml, mean age was 70±/7 years and GS was 7.4±/1.3. The patients with normal scintigraphic finding had statistically significant lower values of serum PSA ($p < 0.0001$) and Gleason score ($p < 0.0001$), comparing to patients with positive bone scan. The correlation between those parameters was better in group of patients with positive bone scan (Spearman correlation $r=0.4$).

Conclusion: The baseline level of PSA more than 50 ng/ml and Gleason score higher than 7 are excellent predictors of positive bone scan in patients with newly diagnosed prostatic cancer.

Key words: Prostatic Neoplasms; Radionuclide Imaging; Neoplasm Grading; Prostate-Specific Antigen; Neoplasm Metastasis; Bone Neoplasms